

D8.1

Project Website, Corporate identity and general templates for dissemination material

Project name

Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes

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	Name	Organisation	Date
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0.2	18/11/2022	Anna Zanetti (ERTC)	Complete draft version ready for internal review
0.3	23/11/2022	Anna Zanetti (ERTC)	Updated draft of the document, based on internal review comments
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1.0	30/11/2022	Dimitrios Liparas (INTRA)	Final submitted version

Legal Disclaimer

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
EU	European Union
IWW	Inland WaterWays
IWAT	Inland Waterways Assessment Tool

Executive Summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to present the PLOT0 project's identifiers to be used for communicating and disseminating the project's outcomes with partners and external stakeholders. More specifically, the document introduces the corporate design and tools developed for the project, including the logo and style guidelines for all project promotional materials, document templates and the project website. In addition, it describes the brand rationale and lays out graphic identity guidelines for the correct use of the logo, brand colours, and typography by the PLOT0 consortium.

1 Introduction

1.1 Project brief description

PLOTO aims at increasing the resilience of the Inland WaterWays (IWW) infrastructures and the connected land infrastructures, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kind of hazards. The project aims to leverage existing tools, as well as emerging ones in order to develop an integrated planning platform called Inland Waterways Assessment Tool (IWAT) that can be primarily applied to Inland Waterways infrastructures.

1.2 Document scope and structure

The purpose of deliverable D8.1 “Project Website, Corporate identity and general templates for dissemination material” is to ensure that the PLOTO brand is represented consistently across all communication materials and dissemination activities. The document presents the corporate design developed for the project, including the logo and style guidelines for all project promotional materials, document templates and the project website. It describes the brand rationale and lays out graphic identity guidelines for the correct use of the logo, brand colours, and typography by the PLOTO consortium.

This document is complementary to PLOTO deliverable D8.2 “Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy 1st version”. Deliverable 8.2 will present a complete communication strategy considering the intended audience, stakeholders, dissemination channels and opportunities, appropriate communication tools, etc. In describing PLOTO’s corporate identity and website, this deliverable focuses on tools developed specifically to fulfil the goals of the communication strategy.

The structure of this deliverable is as follows: Section 1 gives a brief description of the PLOTO project and explains the purpose of this deliverable. Section 2 describes the brand rationale and lays out the graphic identity guidelines for the use of the logo, the colours and the typeface, together with PowerPoint and Word templates available to the PLOTO partners. Sections 3 and 4 depict the printed and the electronic media available for the project, respectively. More specifically, Section 3 describes the project’s leaflet and poster template that will be developed throughout the project’s lifetime, while Section 4 refers to the website structure and social media accounts created to communicate the PLOTO achievements and dissemination opportunities. Finally, Section 5 provides some concluding remarks.

1.3 Intended audience

This is a public document. For the project’s consortium, this document serves as a guide for the use of the PLOTO’s internal and external branding and marketing resources. For interested stakeholders outside of the consortium, it helps to create an understanding of the project’s image and information channels.

2 PLOTO brand

2.1 PLOTO graphic identity and guidelines

The guidelines for correctly representing the PLOTO brand cover all aspects of the project's graphic identity. They describe the rationale of the PLOTO brand, the logo, the logo elements, the logo options, the logo colours, information regarding the incorrect use of it and the PLOTO typography.

2.1.1 Brand rationale

The river as the beating heart of a civilisation

The PLOTO logo (Figure 1) visually captures the river as the engine for mobility and civilisations' prosperity and it symbolically depicts the humans' relationship with this force of nature. The design visually describes the agitated waters, the calm waters and more importantly, the port authorities at the top, strong, equipped, and steady signals along the way.

The PLOTO logo comes in single colour, which makes this logo look modern, clean, and professional. The selected blue evokes the image of the inland waterways, which are they key elements of the project. The typography is simple and direct.

Figure 1. Full PLOTO logo

2.1.2 Master logo

The logo must appear fully intact. It must not be altered or distorted in any way. Guidelines for the correct use of the logo must be respected in terms of the minimum size and colour options. Whenever the logo is used, it should be surrounded by clear space to ensure its visibility and impact. No graphic elements of any kind should enter this zone.

2.1.2.1 Minimum size

At the minimum size, the master logo should always be used in full. All elements must appear in relation to each other as designed. No variation of proportion or position should occur.

2.1.2.2 Colour combination

The PLOTO logo is blue on white background. On a white background, the full colour PLOTO logo should always be used (Figure 2). In situations where the logo must appear on a dark background, the one-colour reserved logo should be used.

Figure 2. PLOTO logo colours

2.1.2.3 Spacing

The PLOTO logo used in any form must not appear at the extreme edge of the page. There must be a minimum clear space (corresponding to the height of the word mark) between it and other elements, including the page edge (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Spacing around logo

2.1.2.4 Incorrect use

The PLOTO logo may not be stretched, distorted or altered. The integrity, proportion, position relative to the word mark and colour identity must be respected. The following images (Figure 4) are examples of wrong usages and alterations that aren't accepted and must be avoided.

Figure 4. Examples of incorrect logo uses

2.1.3 Typography

The Raleway typeface family (Figure 5) will be used for external communication materials, such as brochures, posters, leaflets, roll-up banners and website. The Calibri typeface family (Figure 6) will be used for all working documents, such as Word or PowerPoint templates, for internal and official documents.

Corporate Typeface
RALEWAY

EXTRABOLD
A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

BOLD
A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Corporate Typeface
RALEWAY

REGULAR
A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

LIGHT
A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Figure 5. Primary typeface for external communications

Office Documents Typeface
CALIBRI

BOLD
A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

BOLD ITALIC
A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Office Documents Typeface
CALIBRI

REGULAR
A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

LIGHT
A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Figure 6. Secondary typeface for internal and official communications

2.2 Templates

2.2.1 PowerPoint

A Microsoft PowerPoint (PPT) presentation template for the PLOTO project has been developed (Figure 7). The template consists of slides with the PLOTO logo and includes an opening slide, slides for bullets and tables and a closing slide.

Figure 7. PowerPoint template

A standard project presentation will be developed for use by all consortium partners in their presentations concerning PLOTO.

Consortium partners can access the different elements of the visual identity, including the logo use guidelines, the document templates and standard project presentation via the PLOTO SharePoint.

2.2.2 Other templates (deliverables, meeting’s minute, invitations, press release)

Standard Microsoft Word templates, in keeping with PLOTO brand guidelines, have been developed for PLOTO deliverables (Figure 8), meeting minutes (Figure 9), invitations (Figure 10) and press releases (Figure 11) and are available to the PLOTO consortium partners via the project SharePoint.

Figure 8. Deliverable template

Minutes of Meeting

Title of the Meeting

PROJECT ACRONYM: PLOTO

PROJECT FULL NAME:
Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes.

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER:
101069941 (HORIZON-CLS-2021-06-01-09 – Horizon Innovation Actions)

Date(s)	30/11/2022
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Status - version, date:	Draft – v0.2, 30/11/2022
Dissemination level:	Sensitive (SEN) - limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Reporter(s):	Name Surname
Contributors:	All
Approved by:	Scientific - Technical Committee

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MMT Draft - v0.2, 30/11/2022
Title of the meeting

Document History			
Version	Date	Contributor(s)	Description
0.1	30/11/2022	Name Surname	
0.2	30/11/2022		

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Actions points 3 - H2 14pt..... 3

Participants - H1 - 18 pt

Organisation	Name Surname
RTT	Name Surname
PRTE	Name Surname

Minutes - H1 - 18 pt

- Nemo enim ipsam voluptatem quia voluptas sit aspernatur aut odit aut fugit, sed quia consequuntur mag- ni dolores eos qui ratione voluptatem sequi nesciunt.
- Neque portate velit esse quam nihil molestiae consequatur, vel illum qui dolorem eum fugiat quo voluptas nulla pariatur.
- At vero eos et accusamus et iusto odio dignissimos ducimus qui blanditiis praesentium voluptatum deleniti atque corrupti quos dolores et quas molestias excepturi sint occaecati
- Sed ut perspiciatis unde omnis iste natus error sit voluptatem accusantium doloremque laudantium, totam rem aperiam, eaque ipsa quae ab illo inventore veritatis et quasi architecto beatae vitae dicta sunt explicabo. Nemo enim ipsam voluptatem quia voluptas sit aspernatur aut odit aut fugit, sed quia conse- quuntur magni dolores eos qui ratione voluptatem sequi nesciunt. Neque portate velit esse quam nihil, illum qui dolorem eum fugiat quo voluptas nulla pariatur?

2 Dissemination level: Sensitive (SEN) - limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

ploto-project.eu

Figure 9. Meeting minutes template

Invitation

TO: Mr. Johnnes Spiegel
Manager company

Ploto title lorem ipsum sicut dolet sicut dolet scriptam manet

Subtitle lorem ipsum sicut dolet scriptam manet vecere est
Subtitle lorem ipsum sicut dolet scriptam manet vecere est

DATE: 10.07.2023
TIME: 10:00 -12:30
VENUE: Brussels

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Figure 10. Invitation template

Figure 11. Press release template

2.3 Acknowledgements of EU funds

As the project is co-funded by the European Union, communication and publication materials should clearly acknowledge receipt of EU funding through the display of the EU emblem and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate). The EU funding statement (Figure 12) must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Figure 12. EU funding statement (horizontal and vertical)

- For all communication activities, the EU emblem and funding statement with the following phrase should be used:

"This work is a part of the PLOTO project. This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe innovation actions under grant agreement no. 101069941."

- For infrastructure, equipment & major results, the EU emblem and funding statement with the following phrase should be used:
“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of the PLOTTO project that has received funding from the Horizon Europe innovation actions under grant agreement no. 101069941.”
- For correct use of the EU emblem and funding statement, please use the following link:
European acknowledgement: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

3 Printed media

3.1 Roll-up banner

A roll-up poster will be developed to present the project, its objectives, website, social media and contact addresses, and it will be made available to all consortium partners. It will be used to promote the project at various events and workshops. Further posters may be produced, depending on the need for updates or, during the lifetime of the project, where partners agree on the need for posters dealing with specific results, demonstrations or other aspects of the project.

3.2 Leaflet

A flagship leaflet will be developed early in the project. The document will present the project concepts and will be distributed at PLOT0 events and external conferences, meetings, etc. The leaflet will also be produced in a digital version that will be downloadable from the project website in PDF version and updated as necessary during the project's lifetime.

4 Electronic media

4.1 Website

The PLOTO project website address is www.ploto-project.eu.

4.1.1 Structure and content

The PLOTO website's structure has been created to display information about the project in a transparent and accessible manner. It comprises the following elements:

- **Homepage:**
 - Features a HD image, the tagline and a brief description of the project (Figure 13)
 - Fact & figures (Figure 14): includes basic facts about the project (duration, pilot sites, partners)
 - Project coordinator's logo with active link to the website
 - List of all consortium members with logo and active link to their websites
 - Project's brief description and list of the sub-webpages available, including social media icons
 - Bottom banner with EU flag and reference to the EU funding
- **Objectives** (<https://ploto-project.eu/about/>):
 - Description of the high-level objectives of the PLOTO project (Figure 15)
 - Description of the technological pillars of the project (Figure 16)
- **Pilot sites** (<https://ploto-project.eu/pilot-sites/>) (Figure 17):
 - General description of the pilot sites
 - Detailed description of the activities carried out in each pilot site (Belgium, Hungary and Romania)
 - European map that shows where are located the three pilot sites
- **Library** (<https://ploto-project.eu/library/>):
 - Five sections of documents available, sorted by deliverables, publications, dissemination material, images and videos (Figure 18).
- **News & Events** (<https://ploto-project.eu/news-events/>):
 - On the left, description of the latest news relevant for the PLOTO project
 - On the right, upcoming project events and dissemination opportunities
- **Contact** (<https://ploto-project.eu/contact/>):
 - Contact details of the project coordinator and the communication manager (Figure 19)
 - Contact form to send a message in case of interest (Figure 20)

PLOTO aims at increasing the resilience of the Inland WaterWays (IWW) infrastructures and the connected land infrastructures, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kind of hazards.

Figure 13. Homepage – Hero image and tagline

Figure 14. Homepage - Facts & figures and Partners

Figure 15. Objectives page

Figure 16. Objectives page - Technological pillars

Figure 17. Pilot Sites page

Figure 18. Library page

Figure 19. Contact page - Project Coordinator and Communication Manager contact details

Figure 20. Contact page - Contact us form

4.2 Social media

4.2.1 LinkedIn

A project-specific LinkedIn company page called **PLOTO** has been created (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/plotoproject/?viewAsMember=true>). All major project updates and announcements will be shared with the followers of this page. The page has been launched on 9 November 2022 via the ERTICO biweekly newsletter.

4.2.2 Twitter

The PLOTO Twitter account is called **@PlotoProject**. The account will be used to interact digitally with relevant stakeholders and disseminate the project's activities. Appropriate hashtags will be used to maximise exposure and reach.

4.2.3 YouTube

The PLOTO project has a dedicated YouTube channel, called **Ploto project** (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4gr9srpS_LOKRSKH1CWJLA) that will collect and present all videos that will be created throughout the duration of the project.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable is complementary to the project's Dissemination & Communication Plan (deliverable D8.2). The purpose of the present document is to describe the PLOTO project's communication tools, specifically related to its corporate identity and website. Some printed media are yet to be developed but will be produced in accordance with PLOTO's visual identity and brand.

It is important for all consortium partners to follow the guidelines presented in this deliverable to represent the PLOTO brand consistently. This will allow for the recognition of the project's dissemination activities in a coherent manner.